

An Innovative CMFD-based Acceleration for Pebble-Bed Reactors: the Holed-Grid Finite Difference (HGCMFD) method

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ABSTRACT

High-fidelity neutronic analysis of Pebble-Bed Reactors (PBRs) is computationally demanding due to the absence of regularity along with the strong material heterogeneity arising from the solid fuel pebbles and gaseous coolant. While traditional Coarse Mesh Finite Difference (CMFD) -based methods have been often adopted, these algorithms have shown either limited performance or stability issues in the acceleration of PBR simulations. To address such limitation, a new framework based on arbitrary mesh –including concave shapes– has been proposed, named Holed Grid CMFD (HGCMFD). The proposed method is tailored to properly handle the coarse mesh neutron flux in non-regular reactor cores by selectively separating materials with drastically differing transport properties in different meshes. Such approach prevents the homogenization of flux-peaking areas, like solid fuel pebbles, with flat flux zones, such as gaseous coolant interstices. The scheme is applied to multiple 2D PBR-like problems using an in-house multigroup Finite-Volume Method (FVM). Numerical results demonstrate that HGCMFD improves the stability of CMFD-type accelerations, converging in scenarios where conventional CMFD fails, while outperforming popular partial-current-based CMFD (pCMFD) schemes, depending on the HGCMFD coefficients chosen. The outcomes indicate that HGCMFD is a promising acceleration strategy for heterogeneous reactor systems featuring irregular geometries and strong material heterogeneity, supporting more efficient high-fidelity simulations of PBRs and similar advanced reactor concepts.

Keywords: Holed-Grid CMFD (HGCMFD), CMFD, pCMFD, Pebble-Bed Reactors (PBRs), concave mesh

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently, Pebble-Bed Reactors (PBRs) are the closest to near-term deployment among non-LWRs technologies, thanks to the industrial interest in high-grade heat and hydrogen production. Moreover, the random pebble displacement is one of the key characteristics of PBRs, allowing for the fuel deep-burning [1]. Due to the absence of a regular lattice structure and symmetry within the core, a massive computational burden is imposed in high-fidelity calculations. Additionally, modern multi-physics requirements, such as neutronics and thermal-hydraulic couplings, further increase the resource demand to prohibitive levels

Stochastic and deterministic codes have been extensively developed to solve the eigenvalue problem. To reduce computing time, the Coarse Mesh Finite Difference (CMFD) [2] has been a standard practice for decades. Nonetheless, such technique is proven to be as effective as it is conditionally stable; this drawback is particularly relevant when the optical thickness becomes large or the problem is scattering-dominated. From this perspective, the pCMFD formulation [3] solved the stability issue, but at the cost of reduced acceleration efficiency.

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A critical element of coarse-mesh accelerations is homogenization: even though rigorously performed, it is generally preferable to mix materials with similar properties to minimize deviations in the macroscopic cross sections. In PBRs though, the gaseous coolant and solid pebbles are admixed, homogenizing diverse transport properties. Moreover, due to the absence of regularity, some pebbles may be cut by coarse-mesh boundaries, distorting the local fuel flux distribution: in high-fidelity calculations, these effects can degrade the convergence speed of the scheme.

Motivated by these limitations, this work introduces a generalized CMFD methodology suitable for pebble-bed geometries. The key idea of the Holed-Grid CMFD (HGCMFD) lies in the separation of coolant and pebble meshes by relaxing the convex-mesh assumption: to do so, the method topologically reduces the geometry to a 1D representation, embedding the high-order information into surface- and volume-integrated quantities. In Section 2, the detailed derivation is presented; then, in Section 3, this method is applied to representative PBR-like problems. Such scenarios are evaluated with an in-house deterministic two-group diffusion Finite-Volume Method (FVM) code. The outcomes found are promising, as the CMFD stability range is broadened while obtaining better converging performance compared to the pCMFD logic, underlining the potential for faster and more efficient PBR high-fidelity simulations. Finally, after presenting the numerical results and the sensitivity analysis, in Section 4 the conclusions are drawn.

2. METHODOLOGY

In this section, the Holed-Grid CMFD (HGCMFD) framework is explored; subsequently, the details of the problem solved are presented. The whole derivation is developed in a one-group framework, as a proper energy condensation respecting the Nodal Equivalence Theory preserves the high-order solution [4]. Finally, the sensitivity analysis structure is defined to picture the impact of the user-defined parameters, presented throughout the derivation.

2.1. Derivation

A proper starting point is the one-group integral neutron balance equation, reported in Eq. 1

$$\oint \vec{j} \cdot d\vec{A} + \int \Sigma^{abs} \phi dV = \int \frac{1}{k_{eff}} S_{fiss} dV \quad (1)$$

where on the LHS the \vec{j} is the net neutron current integrated over the control-volume surface, Σ^{abs} is the macroscopic absorption cross section (XS), and ϕ is the scalar neutron flux, both integrated over the control volume, while on the RHS k_{eff} is the effective multiplication factor and S_{fiss} is the fission source.

The integration domain should be discretized in meshes of arbitrary size and shape, mapping the whole domain, and these must be properly interconnected. It is essential to stress this point, as it is pivotal for the proposed framework.

By integrating on the discretized domain composed of arbitrary meshes, Eq. 2 can be obtained

$$J_i A_i + \overline{\Sigma^{abs}_i} \overline{\phi}_i V_i = \frac{1}{k_{eff}} \overline{S_{fiss,i}} V_i \quad (2)$$

where i is the mesh index, J_i is the net neutron leakage from the mesh i , and the over-bar indicates an average over the mesh. A_i and V_i are the mesh total surface and volume, respectively. All the parameters in Eq. 2 must retain the information from the higher-order solution (i.e. from the previous Monte Carlo or transport iteration), due to the nodal equivalence enforcement. Such passage is crucial to avoid

any bias introduction, which may happen due to mesh size-dependent errors. The preservation of the reaction rate terms is imposed via a straightforward flux-volume weighting procedure with energy condensation while the leakage conservation also depends on the neighboring meshes. The latter requires care, particularly for arbitrarily shaped meshes.

To enforce the current preservation, the coarse-mesh based current must be properly modeled. The total number of neutrons leaking from a given mesh could be expressed as a sum of the leakage on each surface, as represented in Eq. 3

$$J_i A_i|_{diff} = \sum_{\Gamma=1}^{N_i} J_{\Gamma,i} A_{\Gamma,i} \quad (3)$$

where Γ indicates the i -th mesh interface and N_i the total number of interfaces. According to diffusion theory, the current on each Γ surface can be derived by imposing the continuity on both sides at the interface r^* , as Eq. 4 shows. By rearranging, the interface coefficient $\tilde{D}_{\Gamma, i, i+1}$ can be expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} J_{\Gamma, i} (r^*) = J_{\Gamma, i+1} (r^*) \\ \phi_{\Gamma, i}^{int} (r^*) = \phi_{\Gamma, i+1}^{int} (r^*) \end{cases} \Rightarrow \tilde{D}_{\Gamma, i, i+1} = \left(\frac{dx}{D_i} + \frac{dl}{D_{i+1}} \right)^{-1} \quad (4)$$

where D_i is the diffusion coefficient of the i -th mesh, while dx and dl are the distances from the mesh center and the interface Γ for the mesh i and $i + 1$, respectively. In this manner, the current $J_{\Gamma, i}$ can be promptly modeled as in Eq. 5

$$J_{\Gamma, i} = -\tilde{D}_{\Gamma, i, i+1} (\phi_{i+1} - \phi_i) \Rightarrow J_i A_i|_{diff} = - \sum_{\Gamma=1}^{N_i} (\tilde{D}_{\Gamma, i, i+1} A_{\Gamma, i}) (\phi_{i+1} - \phi_i) \quad (5)$$

After substituting Eq. 5 into Eq. 3, the mesh total net leakage is determined. To impose the preservation from the reference solution –i.e., the high-order calculation– it is necessary to introduce an error ϵ , as Eq. 6 shows. The current $J|_{ref}$ on the LHS of Eq. 6 is computed from the high-order solution, and it is common to model ϵ as a diffusion-like term [2]. Note that the currents computed are on all the mesh interfaces of the i -th mesh, in contrast to traditional CMFD schemes. By re-elaborating Eq. 6, the correction factor \hat{D}_{i-i+1} for the i -th mesh can be computed.

$$\begin{cases} J_i|_{ref} = J_i|_{diff} + \epsilon \\ \epsilon = -\hat{D} (\phi_{i+1} + \phi_i) \end{cases} \Rightarrow \hat{D}_{i-i+1} = - \frac{J_i|_{ref} - J_i|_{diff}}{\phi_{i+1} + \phi_i} \quad (6)$$

Once the interface diffusion coefficient and the correction factor are modeled, the leakage is preserved and the nodal equivalence grants the invariance of the solution.

So far, no specification was mentioned on the mesh shape. Now, a Pebble Bed Reactor (PBR) can be considered, for example as the LHS in Figure 1. From the previous FVM iteration or Monte Carlo cycle, it is possible to separate the pebbles and the coolant by devising one mesh for each pebble in the reactor; the missing space to properly map the whole domain is covered by one additional randomly-shaped mesh, involving the whole coolant: by doing so, it is possible to map the whole reactor domain with $N_{pebbles} + 1$ meshes. This concept is well illustrated in details of Figure 1.

In realistic configurations, random pebble arrangements involve direct contact between pebbles and with the core boundaries (e.g., the reflector). Since these contacts occur only point-wise, their contribution to neutron transport is assumed negligible. Accordingly, the geometry is approximated by assuming a thin coolant layer between adjacent pebbles is always present.

Figure 1. PBR cross-sectional view on the left, and coarse mesh mapping (one mesh per color)

By applying this simplification, it is then possible to distinguish the pebbles (from now on referenced as Fuel Elements (*FE*)) as convex meshes communicating solely with the concave coolant mesh (referenced as the BackGround (*BG*)), as it is featured by “holes” caused by the pebbles position.

This enables computing the dx and dl coefficients of Eq. 4, as well as all the areas and volumes. Nonetheless, for the *BG* mesh, a representative length is hard to prescribe, since the mesh center may fall in one of the “holes” caused by the pebbles. The distance dl in Eq. 4 is currently constant among all the interfaces, and it is represented in Figure 2. As the correction coefficients grant the leakage preservation in each mesh, imposing different dl values for each mesh theoretically does not affect the nodal balance. However, the magnitude of these coefficients have a relevant effect on the stability and performance of the algorithm; to fully characterize the HGCMFD, their influence has been studied in a sensitivity analysis in the Subsection 3.2, investigating the variation of both dl and dx .

Figure 2. Representative dx and dl lengths in the presented PBR problem.

2.2. Problem Description

To properly test the one-group HGCMFD acceleration, three 2D PBR-like problems have been solved: all of them are two-group problems, with different Fuel Elements (*FE*, in a 3×3 disposition) shapes.

Figure 3. PBR-like problems implemented

Figure 3 depicts the problems solved: intuitively, these 2D examples represent the radial cross-sectional view of a square core, $250 \times 250 \text{ cm}^2$, filled with nine different fuel assemblies. Vacuum is imposed around the core, while the size and shape of the *FE*s have been varied to verify the robustness of the al-

gorithm proposed. Three different *FE* variants have been studied –(*a.1*), (*a.2*), and (*a.3*)– to investigate different scenarios.

Problem (*a.1*) resembles a 3×3 SMR layout, while the variant (*a.2*) rotates the *FEs* by 45° (i.e. rhomboids), enlarging them until a point-wise contact is obtained. Problem (*a.3*) instead, mimics spherical fuel elements (like the pebbles in PBRs) by shaping the *FEs* as octagons. For all the cases, the *FEs* were maintained in the same place, with a distance between the *FE* centers of 80 cm, and the same two-group macroscopic *XS* –reported in Table I– have been used. Problem (*a.1*) has also been used to validate the FVM code by comparison with the in-house deterministic code KANT [5].

Table I. *XS* data. *FE* is relative to the fuel, *MO* to the moderator

	<i>g</i> = 1		<i>g</i> = 2	
	<i>FE</i>	<i>MO</i>	<i>FE</i>	<i>MO</i>
Σ^{tr}	2.21761×10^{-1}	1.21817×10^{-1}	8.80939×10^{-1}	1.251191
Σ^{abs}	9.89250×10^{-3}	8.37939×10^{-4}	9.31542×10^{-2}	2.54031×10^{-2}
$\nu \Sigma^{fis}$	7.36543×10^{-3}	0.00000	1.46524×10^{-1}	0.000000
$\Sigma_{1 \rightarrow}^{scat}$	5.13817×10^{-1}	5.41190×10^{-1}	1.69993×10^{-2}	3.30932×10^{-2}
$\Sigma_{2 \rightarrow}^{scat}$	1.67502×10^{-3}	3.19945×10^{-4}	1.237970	1.942140
χ	1.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000

Additional simulation variables are also reported in Table II. This choice was mainly motivated by a literature review on deterministic codes and empirical evidence for the HGCMFD.

Table II. Simulation options

	Schemes	FVM	HGCMFD
Tolerances			
k_{eff}		10^{-6}	10^{-8}
S_{fiss}		10^{-6}	10^{-8}
Group Sweep.		10^{-6}	10^{-9}
BiCGSTAB		10^{-12}	/

Problem (*a.1*) is formulated to compare both the HGCMFD performance with popular CMFD-like accelerations and the effect a large *BG* mesh has on the calculations. For this problem, the CMFD algorithm very effectively accelerates the code convergence; thus, a comparison in such conditions allows a more objective judgment on the HGCMFD. On the other hand, problems (*a.2*) and (*a.3*) aim to test the algorithm stability when the *BG* mesh becomes less prevalent, meaning the *FE* meshes influence each-other much more; this closely resembles the real PBR scenarios, thus they play a crucial role in the new framework judgment.

2.3. Code Specifications

In this study, a multi-group FVM code has been used to test the HGCMFD compatibility; this ad hoc code was developed to handle square and triangular meshes to properly address all the problem (*a*) cases. Noteworthy, no over- or under-relaxation strategies have been used, as the primary interest is in

testing the stand-alone acceleration framework performance.

2.4. Sensitivity Analysis Details

To further explore the new framework proposed, a sensitivity analysis has been carried out on problem (a.1). The study was conducted with a full grid search technique, testing different values for both dx and dl . A set of 6 values, ranging from 10^{-2} to 20, has been explored, and for all 36 simulations, the convergence behavior of all the key variables acting on the low-order solution, as well as the flux ϕ , both as absolute value and their iteration errors, were carefully monitored. The coefficients' lower and upper boundaries have been selected as extremes, as they sensibly affect the stability and performance of the acceleration technique: for very low dx and dl values, the code exhibits solid stability, while for larger values, performance is boosted until divergence is witnessed.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In the following section, the numerical results are presented and discussed. After having shown the acceleration performance in Subsection 3.1, the sensitivity analysis outcome is thoroughly studied and illustrated in Subsection 3.2, to fully characterize the newly proposed framework.

3.1. Performance Analysis

Figure 4. Convergence behavior for the illustrated problems

In Figure 4 the convergence results for all the problem (a) versions are depicted, comparing the HGCMFD against popular CMFD and pCMFD acceleration schemes: the solid lines represent the Fission Source Distribution (FSD) iteration error, while the dashed lines show the k_{eff} evolution as the outer iterations proceed. Overall, the acceleration has positive effects in most of the cases (diverging cases are excluded), given the minimum speedup among all the cases of 3.10. Noteworthy for problem (a.1) is the HGCMFD performance between the CMFD and the pCMFD ones: The speedup ratio for the conventional CMFD is 61.26, for the HGCMFD of 21.52 and for the pCMFD of 6.08.

For these simulations, the coefficients dx and dl are 10.0 cm and 0.01 cm, respectively, and they have been selected mixing physical considerations (i.e. FE side) and computation efficiency, pursuing a favorable trade-off between performance and stability. Care should be taken in the dx and dl selection: as it can be understood by comparing the physical center-to-side distance, the dx shares only the order of magnitude, but not the exact geometric value: it has been found that, particularly for problem (a.2) and (a.3), the same physical value led to divergence. Such behavior is under further investigation, because large instability is mainly manifested when the HGCMFD uses condensed XS.

The solutions for these problems are based on a mesh size of $\delta x = \delta y = 1.25$ cm; in case of the triangular meshes, rectangular isosceles triangles have been chosen. Figure 4 not only exhibits the CMFD

effectiveness in (a.1), but it also highlights how in problem (a.2) and (a.3) the same algorithm fails, while the HGCMFD and the pCMFD converge effectively. Moreover, HGCMFD represents a compromise between CMFD and pCMFD, combining the high computational efficiency of CMFD with the enhanced stability characteristics of pCMFD: in fact, it is appreciable how the performance compared to the pCMFD is always superior and converging, effectively accelerating the numerical scheme, compared with the CMFD algorithm, successfully working only in (a.1).

After the convergence behavior, the converged flux must be analyzed to rigorously check that no bias due to the acceleration has been introduced. Table III shows the maximum, minimum, mean, and root-mean-squared errors (RMSE) of the relative difference between the accelerated and not accelerated fluxes. Note that the RMSE in this case is exploited to better visualize how the discrepancy is distributed over the domain, while the L2 norm is omitted as set as convergence criterion. In this comparison, only problem (a.1) is examined, as it is the only case where the CMFD converges, and it must be highlighted the numbers are well above the variables double precision. It is noteworthy how the separation of the local peaking flux areas improves the flux estimation, as the HGCMFD has a lower discrepancy compared to the CMFD-accelerated solution; nonetheless, the pCMFD shows instead a better flux handling, underlining the partial currents formulation effectiveness regardless of the grid logic.

Table III. Error analysis for all the problems in (a) in permille

%	(a.1)		
	CMFD	pCMFD	HGCMFD
Max (θ)	0.240	0.011	0.139
Min (θ)	-0.173	-0.004	-0.063
Mean (θ)	-0.036	-0.001	-0.005
RMSE (θ)	0.129	0.004	0.052

3.2. Sensitivity Analysis

In the second part of Section 3, a concise sensitivity analysis varying the dx and dl terms is necessary to properly grasp the versatility of the HGCMFD, as well as to have deeper insights on how acceleration algorithms actually affect the numerical simulations.

Figure 5. Outer iterations as function of the dx (left) and dl (right). Sensitivity outcomes in the center

A heatmap on the left of Figure 5 displays presents the sensitivity results, showing the prevalent effect of dl on the method convergence. By fixing the dx value, as more geometrically explicit, on the right chart of Figure5, the optimum trend of the outer iterations as dl varies suggests a numerics-related issue, thus

all the HGCMFD variables' evolution has been tracked. In CMFD-based algorithms, the ratio between the correction factors $\hat{D}_{i, i+1}$ and the interface coefficient $\bar{D}_{i, i+1}$ is of particular importance. Such ratio in the HGCMFD drifts from negative towards positive values as dx or dl increase; when divergence occurs, $\hat{D}_{i, i+1}/\bar{D}_{i, i+1}$ is larger than 1.0. Such threshold could be used as a proper discrimination procedure for an optimal dl and dx selection.

4. CONCLUSIONS

To address the growing concerns regarding the computational burden of high-fidelity calculations, the presented work introduces a generalized CMFD-like acceleration framework, enabling faster convergence for Pebble Bed Reactor (PBR)-like neutronic analysis. The key point of the Holed-Grid Coarse Mesh Finite Difference (HGCMFD) method is related to common issues associated with homogenization in reactor analysis, particularly when the domain is neither symmetric nor regular.

By relaxing the convex mesh hypothesis, the separation of coolant and fuel elements is enforced. The distinction in separate meshes of the solid fuel materials and the gaseous background in the reactor core reduces the discrepancies between the real and condensed data, while allowing a separate treatment of local power peaking zones from flat flux areas: such a feature enhances the precision in the flux estimation, leading to better convergence performance. All these characteristics are reflected in a broadening of the stability range and versatility compared to traditional CMFD algorithms, as demonstrated in the first part of the numerical results proposed in this study.

In the second part, the code has been thoroughly analyzed in different scenarios, stressing the core assumptions of the formulation illustrated: although the code has revealed a sensitive dependency on the two coefficients dx and dl , formally representing in the formulation physical distances, its implementation accelerated the convergence of problems where traditional CMFD algorithms failed, while exhibiting superior performance compared to popular pCMFD accelerations.

Concluding, the HGCMFD demonstrates strong potential for PBR problems, or any other reactor in which exotic elements challenge traditional CMFD schemes. Nonetheless, additional work should be carried out in the framework stability direction, such as the implementation of a partial-currents-based formulation, as well as stress-testing the algorithm on more realistic problems. The numerical results shown encourage improved accessibility to high-fidelity calculations, as well as more detailed transient simulations for non-regular reactors.

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